

An Introduction on International Commerce Research in Borneo

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ABSTRACT

Borneo is one of the biggest islands in the world with a relatively big market size. Borneo administratively belongs to three countries which are Brunei, Indonesia and Malaysia. Brunei is known as oil rich nation. Kalimantan Indonesia are known for its coal and other resources. Sabah and Sarawak are known for being rich in oil and gas, palm oil and its tourism activities. After saying that, does these three countries have commerce transaction much with each other? This paper reviews some research that attempts to discuss commerce transaction in these nations.

Keyword: commerce, trade, resources

INTRODUCTION

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International trade or commerce has been in existence for hundreds or even thousands of years in Borneo. Movement of goods have been there for centuries. Malaysia and Brunei and located strategically facing the South China Sea. Parts of Kalimantan are seen close to Singapore.

Trade have gradually improved from time to time. Opening of ports and infrastructure upgrading has been ongoing. Looking at current situation, does these

The work of R. Idris (2018) has attempted to estimate the impact of Sabah-Kalimantan road connectivity on Sabah's export. The author uses gravity model to explain the effects of road connecting Sabah and Kalimantan via international trade. He uses Malaysian experience as a basis for his conclusion looking from Malaysian perspective.

The work of R. Idris et. al (2017) have looked at Sabah-Kalimantan road connectivity from cultural affinity effects on Sabah's Export. The findings reveal that cultural affinity do play role in increasing Sabah's export.

R. Idris, K. Mansur and Marso (2019) discusses the economy of Kalimantan. The article explains the economy of five provinces in Kalimantan based on several highly aggregated sectors. Few provinces are important for coal related activities while other areas are good at agricultural and other resources.

R. Idris and A. Majid (2018) have surveyed Malaysian consumer products which are available in the city of Tarakan, North Kalimantan. The report reveals a long list of products of Malaysian products which have demand in North Kalimantan.

There are many other studies on Borneo such as on intra-economic activities, economic activities in each state/province/country, issues in commerce and economic potentials of Borneo. This can be seen for example in the work of Mahmud Thoha (2008), R. Idris, R. Z. Idris and Sidah Idris (2019), R. Idris (2019), R. Idris and K. Mansur (2018 a), R. Idris and R. Idris (2018), R. Idris and K. Mansur (2018 b), R. Idris and K. Mansur (2018 c).

The selected review clearly shows that effort to research on trade activities within Borneo is of growing interest. Not much work seen in relation to Brunei and its link with other Borneo counterparts. However, there are some official are useful, such as WTO (2008) and World Tourism Organization and World Trade Organization

(2015). There are still big gaps that need to be filled, to really understand commerce in Borneo. Areas such as sectors that can be complement to each other should be focused.

CONCLUDING REMARK

Studies in Borneo business activities are rising and awareness have increased. More specific research on commerce activities within is important. Recent research work such as by R. Idris in recent years should be continued and further expanded. More work need to be done on this third most biggest island in the world.

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